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Application of One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in Exploring Municipal Solid Waste Characteristics in Kano Metropolis, Northwestern Nigeria

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

This study describes the characteristics of municipal solid waste generated in Kano metropolis, Nigeria. Samples of Municipal solid waste from dumps located within three residential zones of Kano metropolis were collected and segregated into their various components based on the ATSM standards. The results indicated a predominance of organic and biodegradable matter 66%, while non biodegradable waste accounted for 34%, but with marked variation among the different zones. Post Hoc analysis from one way ANOVA shows the City and GRA have mean differences of 26.20000* (Turkey HSD), City and GRA have 26.20000* (LSD), and city and GRA 26.0000* (Bonferroni). All the 3 post hoc measure agree that there are significant differences in the mean of solid waste generation between city and GRA. Skewness ranged from - 0.717 to 0.744 indicating a normal distribution. The observed variation has implication for the frequency of collection, storage, transport disposal, choice and suitability of equipments, health of the inhabitants and the environment.

Keywords: Biodegradable, Non-biodegradable, waste statistics, waste segregation, waste composition.

INTRODUCTION

Municipal solid waste is a complex endeavor due to the huge quantities that is generated daily in cities, and also to the fact that municipal solid waste is dynamic, cultural, economical and specific. Due to its complexity, it is necessary to have reasonably accurate and up to date not only on the quantity of waste that is generated in a particular area, but the composition and characteristics.

In Nigeria, globalization and population growth have accelerated the dynamics of the urbanization process with unprecedented growth rates of cities which has left them deficient in basic infrastructural services like water supply, sewage and solid waste management. Due to lack of serious planning, capacity, inefficiency and poor funding, the management of especially municipal solid waste has become a tenacious problem.

A particular source of uncertainty in the efficient management of municipal solid waste is the lack of information of both present and future characteristics of waste that is generated. Yet, a good long-term plan for waste management should specify what characteristics of the present and future generation is in order to plan for the appropriate facilities to be provided for the transfer, treatment, recycling or disposal of wastes, where and when those facilities are to be built, and to what capacity .

Presently, cities in Nigeria including Kano metropolis do not have data on waste characteristics and where it exists, it is incomplete, inconsistent and unreliable due to wide variations in data recording, definitions, collection methods and seasonal variations.

In recent years models have been developed to evaluate waste management strategies using various techniques and relationship in order to mitigate the lack of reliable data in developing countries. Adedibu (1985) calculated correlation coefficients between different waste components and socio-economic variables of income, education and household size. However, correlation analysis determines the relationship between two variables, but does not provide any information on which variable is dependent on the other and it cannot demonstrate the form of the relationship which can be defined as the nature of the control that one variable exerts over the other (Walford, 1995). Moreover, bivariate correlations are not satisfactory considering the complex dynamics of waste generation

process since they do not give information about combined effects of more than one factor. This paper describes the characteristics of waste generated in Kano metropolis and highlights its implication to waste management strategy.

Description of the Study Area

Kano is the largest city in the Sudan Region of West Africa. It is located between latitude 12° 25 N to 12° 40 N and longitude 8° 35 N to 8° 45 E and has for centuries been the most important commercial and industrial nerve centre attracting millions from all parts of the region and beyond. Immigration and natural growth rate of 3% and rapid economic activities is expected to continue to increase the population and waste stream in the years to come. Today Kano metropolis generates about 1,0805,000 tons of solid waste per year or approximately 3050 metric tons per day (Nabegu, 2008a). By 2025, this figure is expected to increase to 1,825,000 tons per year, or 5000 metric tons per day. These are estimates and the real values are probably more than these quantities. The climate of the study area is the tropical wet and dry Aw by Koppen's classification. Climatic factors play a crucial role in the municipal waste management of the study area. For example, during the wet season, heat and humidity cause the municipal solid waste to be of higher moisture content thus increasing the weight of the refuse (Nabegu, 2008b). In addition, high humidity with heat causes the organic portion of the waste to decompose quickly leading to problems in handling and disposal, which directly affects the environmental health of the waste workers and the inhabitants (Kurupran et al., 2003).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was undertaken between March and May 2007 and was organized in stages as follows:

Stage 1: This stage involved a desk study in which documents and records relating to municipal solid waste management in Kano metropolis, by the state agency responsible for waste management, the Refuse Management and Sanitation Board (REMASAB), were studied to obtain archival data on existing municipal solid waste composition.

Stage 2: To determine sample locations within Kano metropolis, a basic knowledge of the urban area of Kano was helpful, guided by the assertion of Gordon (1983) that an urban area is usually defined to comprise of three levels within which data could be collected: - The city proper (in this study the old walled city): - Metropolitan transition area (in this study the G.R.A.) and urban agglomeration (in this study suburban area). These represented various residential, commercial, market, and industrial areas. One dump site in each of the three identified residential zones was selected randomly.

Stage 3: The general principles outlined by ASTM (1999) were followed. The waste from identified dump site in each area was thoroughly mixed. 100 kg of sample was collected. A quartering technique based on NEERI (Report, 1997) was used to obtain 12.5 kg. Using the quartering technique, the total waste mass was divided into four parts and waste from two diagonally opposite portions was taken and mixed. The other two portions were discarded. This procedure was repeated until a waste sample of approximately 12.5 kg weight was obtained. The technique was done daily in each dump site for three months.

Stage 4: Various components from the daily 12.5 kg sample, such as plastics, paper, metal, organic fractions, etc., were segregated and weighed and the mean for each site was taken and expressed as a percentage of the total weight.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the different categories of waste observed in the three residential zones of Kano metropolis. From the samples of solid wastes collected in the three zones, eight different types of wastes were categorized. These are food scrap, paper cardboard, textile and rubber, plastic material, glass, metal, ash, dirt and vegetables. The mean range from 2 to 15 kg in residential areas with card board waste being the highest waste generated in the study area. The skewness value of the data ranges from 0.742 to -0.736, which is within the acceptable limit of ± 2 . The Kurtosis value of these data is -1.554 which is within the acceptable limit.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of solid waste components found in Kano metropolis

Waste type	Mean	SE	SD	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
	2	0.15162	0.83045	0.69	0	-1.554
Food scrap	27.6	2.97136	16.2748	264.869	-0.736	-1.553
Cardboard	15	2.49597	13.67101	186.897	0.742	-1.554
Textile Rubber	7	0.45486	2.49136	6.207	0	-1.554
Metals	9.3333	1.40878	7.71623	59.54	0.706	-1.554
Plastic	11	0.84418	4.62378	21.379	0.336	-1.554
Glass	6.6667	0.83506	4.57379	20.92	-0.117	-1.554
Ash	13	1.58296	8.6702	75.172	-0.714	-1.554
Vegetable	10.3333	1.52627	8.35973	69.885	0.252	-1.554

Source: Field work, 2007.

Analysis of waste type in Table 2 shows that Kano metropolis's solid waste consists of 66% organic and biodegradable matter and 34% non biodegradable typical of low income developing country (Ramachandra and Bachanda, 2007). However, further observation of the table indicates that the mean values of the components show variations in the composition within the city.

Table 2: Waste Categories Collected

Categories	City	G.R.A.	Suburban
Food scrap	38	5	40
Paper cardboard	6	34	5
Textile rubber	7	10	4
Plastic material	10	17	6
Metal	5	20	3
Glass	7	12	1
Ash, dirt	18	1	20
Vegetable	9	1	21

Source: Field Work, 2007.

Variation within the different parts of the city is further established in Table 3 where, the Post Hoc analysis from one way ANOVA, indicates that, the City and GRA have mean differences of 26.20000* (Turkey HSD), City and GRA have 26.20000* (LSD), and city and GRA 26.0000* (Bonferroni). All the 3 post hoc measure agree that there are significant differences in the mean of solid waste composition between the city and GRA. This can be explained by the fact that, in high income areas, disposable material and packaged food are used in higher quantities which results in the waste having higher calorific value, lower specific density and lower moisture content. In the case of lower income areas, the usage of fresh vegetables is much higher and mostly materials that are reusable are used. This results in a waste composition that has high moisture content, high specific weight and low calorific value. Similar pattern were reported elsewhere by Abu Qdais et al. (1997), Dennison et al. (1996), Ramachandra and Bachanda, (2007), Buenrostro *et al.* (2001) and Gómez *et al.* (2009) among others.

Table 3: Post Hoc comparison of the waste components observed in the three sites

Dependent Variable: Food scrap							
						95% Confidence Interval	
	(I) Areas	(J) Areas	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Tukey HSD	City	GRA	26.20000*	3.93371	0	16.4467	35.9533
		Suburban	-4.9	3.93371	0.437	-14.6533	4.8533
	GRA	City	-26.20000*	3.93371	0	-35.9533	-16.4467
		Suburban	-31.10000*	3.93371	0	-40.8533	-21.3467
	Suburban	City	4.9	3.93371	0.437	-4.8533	14.6533
		GRA	31.10000*	3.93371	0	21.3467	40.8533
LSD	City	GRA	26.20000*	3.93371	0	18.1287	34.2713
		Suburban	-4.9	3.93371	0.224	-12.9713	3.1713
	GRA	City	-26.20000*	3.93371	0	-34.2713	-18.1287
		Suburban	-31.10000*	3.93371	0	-39.1713	-23.0287
	Suburban	City	4.9	3.93371	0.224	-3.1713	12.9713
		GRA	31.10000*	3.93371	0	23.0287	39.1713
Bonferroni	City	GRA	26.20000*	3.93371	0	16.1594	36.2406
		Suburban	-4.9	3.93371	0.671	-14.9406	5.1406
	GRA	City	-26.20000*	3.93371	0	-36.2406	-16.1594
		Suburban	-31.10000*	3.93371	0	-41.1406	-21.0594
	Suburban	City	4.9	3.93371	0.671	-5.1406	14.9406
		GRA	31.10000*	3.93371	0	21.0594	41.1406
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.							

In a similar study, Banar and Özkan (2008) compared the percentage of waste components between socio-economic levels stratified by income. They further calculated the correlation coefficients between income and waste components. Waste components except for food waste and ash were found to be positively related to income level. Negative correlation of ash was attributed to the usage of coal as a fuel in low-income group. Although food wastes were lower in amount in high socio-economic level, the packaging wastes were higher and the results showed that moisture content decreased with increasing income level. The direction of the relation depends on many other factors which are in essence related to different lifestyles. The differences can be observed in heating means, nutritional habits, preferences on purchased products and many other lifestyle habits. However, income may not be the sole indicator while observing the impact of different lifestyles.

For example, a different stratification was carried out in United Kingdom by Emery, *et al.* (2003). They used a classification system based on dwelling types with the help of a geo-demographic information system called ACORN. The residents living in modern semi-detached houses, which denoted the high prosperity level, were found to generate far more waste per household, which is consistent with outcome of other studies. These households produced more packaging materials due to higher consumption of comestibles.

Household studies have been used elsewhere, and they enable relationships between waste quantity and a broad set of individual characteristics or habits of either the household itself or the household's representative to be analyzed (Abu Qdais *et al.*, 1997; Dennison *et al.*, 1996). Positive experience with regards to the relationship between settlement structure and waste generation characteristics as the attempt in this study corroborates the selection of homogeneous settlement areas as the sample unit. Homogeneity of settlement and dwelling types in a given area is assumed to implicitly control variables such as income, employment status and household size. Thus, the pattern of waste constituents between the different parts of Kano metropolis reflects the difference in consumption pattern, cultural and educational differences.

However, according to (US EPA, 1999), differences in the characterization and reporting of waste types also differ with some municipal authorities and within metropolises including for instance, the inclusion of construction and demolition of waste and industrial waste as part of the municipal waste stream. Some inter-urban differences relate to climate also (Kurupran et al., 2003). Moreover, differences in basic infrastructure bring other variations in cities with unpaved or poorly paved streets that have large amounts of dust and dirt from street sweeping. There are big differences in amounts of organic waste among cities according to the number of trees and shrubs in public places (Dyson and Chang, 2005).

Implications of Results to Municipal Solid Waste Management

Differences in the composition of wastes observed in the three residential zones of Kano metropolis has implication for storage and collection such that the city and the suburban zones which generate wastes that are more susceptible to decomposition should have some form of corrosion-resistant container with lids in order to facilitate collection. Lidded containers would also exclude most animal pests, reduce the amount of rainfall soaking into garbage and help to reduce trash blowing about on the street, rather than the practice now where the waste are dumped on the ground.

Transport of waste from households and other generation sites is a growing problem. Rapid urbanization of Kano metropolis leaves little time for adequate layout and planning; especially the sub urban areas at the periphery of existing settlement. Waste dumps, with their associated disease, odor and frequent fires would ideally be located on suitable land away from the most densely populated areas. These areas are becoming harder to find as population urbanize and municipal traffic increases; the transport of waste becomes longer and more time-consuming, and therefore more expensive and less efficient. Many residents of the city and the suburban areas employ neighborhood-level collection points, where households are responsible for transport to the transfer point and the government transports the waste from there to the ultimate disposal location. Transport also relies on operational vehicles, and frequent breakdowns coupled with parts shortages can immobilize collection vehicles for extended periods of time. Aside from the obvious health implications, the concentrations of people in the city and suburban zones further complicate transport and unloading procedures and present numerous safety and logistical concerns. Further, many people, not only those residing near landfills, make their living from scavenging on solid waste before it enters the municipal waste stream.

Presence of non-biodegradable wastes could lead to economic utilization of such wastes, since the recycling and re-use of non-biodegradable wastes into new forms is now a common practice. Though informally organized, it provides a substantial employment in view of the fact that ready a market exists in the many industrial enterprises located in Kano. Biodegradable wastes which are generated in very high quantity could be of high economic value since they could serve as source of biofertilizer, biogas and animal feed. This has not been utilized. However, as a result of the dearth and high cost of chemical fertilizers, farmers directly use domestic waste in agriculture (Nabegu, 2008c). Thus, a waste management strategy for the city should focus on managing biodegradable organic waste, considering this fraction has the potential to impact the quality of leachate and gas generation if deposited in a sanitary landfill.

An important observation in this study is the use of location and settlement type as a surrogate to income, economic and social determinants. Clearly, the nature and type of settlements as used in this study could be more realistic in developing countries than the evaluation of households based on their economic or social status due to the difficulty of determining actual income and the fact that often times such information is hardly given correctly and the fact that status do change. Consequently, one of the implications of this study is the fact that settlement type whether high income, suburban or shanty can be used to establish a realistic relationship between waste type and type of settlement.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion drawn from this limited study is that the management of municipal solid waste would have to involve detailed study of the characteristics of waste as the variation in waste type and composition impact on human health, environment and all the processes of waste management system from the storage, collection, transport disposal and choice of equipments. Furthermore, the variation in the composition of waste observed within the three different residential zones of Kano metropolis reflects local variation in standard of living and indicate that to achieve success in management, waste should be managed at the local level instead of the current practice of having a large centralized agency so that local variations can be taken into account. Any waste management framework for Kano metropolis must take into account these issues. Consequently, a careful consideration of all these factors in relation to local conditions must be the basis of a sound and sustainable waste management programme.

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